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An application of two-factor theory to IT knowledge workers in Sri Lanka

Abstract

This paper investigates the factors that motivate IT knowledge workers by applying Herzberg's two-factor theory. In the study, a survey questionnaire was used, and 159 randomly selected IT knowledge workers (all graduates) working in software development companies responded. The data was analyzed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences. The findings gave an insight into the factors that motivate IT knowledge workers in Sri Lanka. Further analysis revealed that the motivational factors do not vary by age, gender, civil status, the number of years of service in the current company, or the number of employees in a company. The findings led to the conclusion that the order of motivational factors in the Sri Lankan context was not similar to that of the order of findings of Herzberg's study. The findings implied that IT organizations need to pay special attention to motivational factors of IT knowledge workers in designing jobs and in motivating them.

Keywords: IT industry, Knowledge workers, Motivation, Sri Lanka, Two-Factor Theory

1. Introduction

The information technology (IT) industry builds on knowledge workers. Absorbing and retaining qualified employees is the focal point for the success of any IT organization. In the competitive Sri Lankan IT labour market, companies make substantial investments to adopt various strategies to recruit and retain qualified knowledge workers. In this context, an understanding of motivational factors of knowledge workers is essential. Though research on motivation produced some solid evidence on what motivates information system (IS) staff, most, if not all, of such studies are restricted to information system staff in the USA. The answer to the question "can these findings be generalized to IT knowledge workers in other countries?" requires replicating USA-based studies in other environments where the social, economic, and cultural characteristics are fundamentally different. Hence, to strengthen the external validity of the USA-based motivation research findings, its international dimension (Aharoni and Burton, 1994; Rosenzweig, 1994) needs to be validated using cross-cultural research. However, published literature in the field of motivation in the Sri Lankan context is rare. To fill this gap, this study made an investigation into motivational factors of IT knowledge workers in the software development organizations in Sri Lanka based on one of the famous content theories

of work motivation, i.e., Herzberg's two-factor theory (Herzberg, 1966, 1987). The specific objectives of the investigation are:

- to investigate and evaluate the preferred motivation factors of IT knowledge workers in Sri Lanka based on Herzberg's two-factor theory.
- to compare the motivational potential score of the two-factor theory (MPS_{TFT}) across personal demographic factors, such as age, gender, civil status, the number of years of experience in the current organization, and total years of service in the IT field, and the number of employees in a company.

2. Literature review

2.1 Motivation

In general, motivation deals with forces that initiate, direct, and sustain behaviour towards the attainment of certain goals (Analoui 2000; Bent et al., 1999; Luthans 1995; Mullins 1999). Specifically, in the organizational context, motivation focuses on the willingness to exert high levels of effort towards organizational goals, conditioned by the effort's ability to satisfy some individual needs (Robbins, 1998). Work motivation is influenced by a large number of factors in the organizational environment (Steers and Porter, 1991). Content or needs theories, represented by Maslow (1954), Alderfer (1969), McClelland (1961), and Herzberg (1966), suggest that individuals are motivated by internal needs and organizations should identify and directly apply these needs to the structure of work.

2.2 Herzberg's two-factor theory of motivation

Herzberg (1966) identified that job satisfaction and dissatisfaction emerged from two sets of factors: dissatisfiers (hygiene factors) and satisfiers (motivating factors). Hygiene factors that affected the context in which work is conducted included factors such as salary, working conditions, and relationships with superiors. Motivation factors that are related to job context and rewards of work performance included factors such as achievement, recognition, and advancement. The hygiene factors are extrinsic- they aim to prevent job dissatisfaction, and have little contribution in creating positive feelings towards the job. Motivators, on the other hand, are intrinsic elements of the job- they encourage personal growth and development, and contribute very little to job dissatisfaction. Further, the factors that provide job satisfaction are separate and distinct from the factors that lead to work dissatisfaction. Herzberg (1966, 1987) and Herzberg et al (1999) described that positive and negative attitudes towards the job are not the opposite of each other, since they are influenced by different factors. Therefore, they suggested that the opposite of job satisfaction is *no job satisfaction*, and the opposite of job dissatisfaction is *no job dissatisfaction*. However, both the hygiene factors and the motivators fulfill an individual's needs. In discussing *the* theory, Herzberg (1966) identified two types of

employees in the workplace, hygiene seekers and motivation seekers, where hygiene seekers have an external locus of control and are extrinsically motivated, while motivation seekers have an internal locus of control and are intrinsically motivated (Herzberg, 1966).

3. Methodology

3.1 Conceptual framework

For the study, an IT knowledge worker is defined as a professional who is working in a software development company in Sri Lanka with at least a bachelor's degree or membership of a professional body such as BCS, IEE, or IESL. **Figure 1** shows the framework developed for the investigation, in which it is proposed that work motivation of IT professionals is a result of the interaction between personal demographic factors and IT professionals' needs.

3.2 Hypothesis

Literature reveals that about two decades ago, the general community was not familiar with computers. The individuals who worked in this field about two decades ago were very specialized and motivated largely by the intrinsic rewards inherent in the work itself (Harry and Edward, 1998). With the growing use of computers, the demand for software workers has increased enormously. Thus, working with software has become an attractive occupation with a variety of external motivators (Harry and Edward, 1998). Further, Salancik and Pfeffer's social information processing theory (1978) also suggests that since software-related jobs provide good work and career conditions, individuals do not have to explain their career choice or job satisfaction by intrinsic motivation. The extrinsic motivation provides sufficient explanation, and individuals will not report intrinsic motivation. Therefore, to detect shifts, if there are any, in intrinsic and extrinsic motivation in the Sri Lankan context, it is hypothesised:

H1: When motivation and hygiene factors are ranked in order of magnitude, the ranking order is different from that of Herzberg's findings

Figure 1 - Factors contribute to work motivation of IT professionals

3.3. Sample

The study was conducted using the survey method. A self-administered survey questionnaire was distributed among a randomly selected sample of IT professionals working in software development companies in Sri Lanka. For the study, 159 valid responses were received. The diversity of the sample is achieved with respect to gender, age, civil status, designation, the years of service in the current work organization, and total service in the IT field. Table 1 shows the sample profile. After analysing the questionnaire data, personal discussions were conducted to gain a deeper insight into the results with randomly selected respondents covering the respective subgroups of the sample.

Table 1 - Sample profile

Demographics Factors		Count	Demographics Factors		Count
Age	28 or below	77	Service in Current Company	Less than 2	60
	29-32	51		2-4	44
	More than 33	31		More than 5	55
Gender	Male	118	Total Service in IT field	Less than 4	76
	Female	41		4-7	62
Civil Status	Single	88		More than 8	21
	Married	71	No of Employees	Less than 50	26
Educational Qualification	Graduate	142		50-200	26
	Post Graduate	17		201-500	95
Designation	Manager	15		More than 501	12
	Programmer	124			
	Technical	8			
	Consultant	12			

3.4. Methods of data analyses

The questionnaire consisted of two columns (i.e., [a] & [b]) with respect to factors described in the two-factor theory. The column (a) dealt with the actual situation at work, whereas the column (b) considered the satisfaction, as shown in Table 2.

Table 2 - Mapping between scales in the questionnaire and analysis scale

	Hygiene ←————→ Motivator			
Defined scale for analysis	-2	-1	1	2
Defined scale in the questionnaire for column (a)	Very Low	Low	High	Very High
Defined scale in the questionnaire for column (b)	Very dissatisfied	Dissatisfied	Satisfied	Very satisfied

To calculate percentage frequencies for each factor, the mean value of (a) and (b) for each factor for each individual was calculated using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) software. To calculate the motivator percentage frequency for each factor, percentage frequencies greater than zero were accumulated. To calculate the hygiene percentage frequency

for each factor, percentage frequencies less than zero were accumulated. When the calculations of columns (a) and (b) resulted in zero percentage frequency, it was considered a neutral result. Defined scale for analysis varied from -32 to 0 or 0 to +32 since 16 factors were analyzed (i.e., $16 \times -2 = -32$ and $16 \times 2 = 32$). The motivational potential score of the two-factor theory (MPS_{TFT}) was defined for each individual as follows and was used to calculate an overall measure of positive internal work motivation from personal needs.

$$MPS_{TFT} = \sum_{i=1 \rightarrow 16} (\text{Mean value of factor})$$

Thereafter, the percentage of the MPS_{TFT} for each individual was calculated as follows.

$$MPS_{TFT} \% = (MPS_{TFT}/32) \times 100$$

4. Results

4.1 Preferred motivation factors of IT professionals in software companies

The rankings of the factors were shown in Figure 2. As shown in Figure 2, all factors except advancement were ranked as motivation factors. Advancement was not ranked as a motivation factor. According to Herzberg (1966, 1987), advancement is a motivation factor. Achievement was the highest-ranking factor towards motivation in the study, and this is in line with Herzberg's findings.

Figure 2 – Comparison of satisfiers and Dissatisfiers

Further, according to Table 2, relationships with peers, superiors, and subordinates become the 2nd, 3rd, and 4th most important factors, respectively. The general tendency of the findings was that most of the hygiene factors, which were defined by Herzberg, move towards the motivation direction, while most of the motivation factors, which were defined by Herzberg (1966, 1987), become less important motivation factors. Thus, the hypothesis of the study has been supported by the findings.

Table 3 shows rankings for demographic groupings of age, gender, civil status, service in the current company, total service in the IT field, and the number of employees in the company. Advancement was consistently the lowest-ranked factor across all groupings. Overall, major deviations from the overall rankings of motivational factors have not been evident across demographic groupings and the grouping of the number of employees in the company.

Table 3: Rankings for demographic groupings of age, gender, civil status, service in the current company, total service in the IT field, and the number of employees in the company

Overall Rank	Herzberg's Factors	Age			Gender		Civil Status		Current Service			Total Service			No of Employee				
		28 or below	29-32	33 or more	Male	Female	Single	Married	Less than 2	2-4	5 or more	Less than 4	4-7	8 or more	than 50	50-200	201-500	501 or more	
1	Achievement	2	1	1	2	1	1	1	2	1	1	2	1	2	1	1	1	1	1
2	Relationship with peers	1	2	3	1	3	2	2	1	2	3	1	2	3	2	4	2	2	2
3	Relationship with supervisor	4	3	2	3	4	4	3	3	5	2	3	3	1	5	3	4	4	4
4	Relationship with subordinates	3	4	5	4	5	3	4	4	3	4	4	4	4	6	8	3	3	3
5	Status	5	6	7	7	2	5	7	5	7	6	8	5	7	7	6	6	6	6
6	Responsibility	8	5	4	5	6	6	6	8	6	5	7	6	5	9	7	5	5	5
7	Working condition	7	7	6	6	10	8	5	6	4	8	5	8	6	4	10	8	8	8
8	Supervision	6	10	10	8	7	7	8	7	10	7	10	7	9	8	13	7	7	7
9	Recognition	11	8	11	9	12	9	10	9	9	11	6	10	10	10	2	10	10	10
10	Company policy & administration	9	13	9	11	8	12	9	10	13	9	11	9	11	13	9	9	9	9
11	Work itself	12	9	13	10	11	11	11	11	8	12	9	12	8	3	5	14	14	14
12	Security	10	12	14	12	9	10	13	12	11	14	12	11	12	11	12	12	12	12
13	Personal life	14	14	8	13	13	15	12	14	15	10	14	13	13	15	11	11	11	11
14	Salary	13	15	12	14	15	13	15	15	14	13	15	15	14	14	15	13	13	13
15	Growth	15	11	15	15	14	14	14	13	12	15	13	14	15	12	14	15	15	15
16	Advancement	16	16	16	16	16	16	16	16	16	16	16	16	16	16	16	16	16	16

4.2 Compare MPS_{TFT} with personal demographics

Motivation potential score was calculated to analyse variations in personal demographics in overall motivation. Figures 3 to 8 show the results. As shown in Figure 3, the overall work motivation of IT professionals who belong to the age group of 28 years or below was higher than that of all other age groups. According to Figure 4, the work motivation of females was higher than that of men.

Figure 3 - Mean value of % of MPS_{TFT} variation with age

Figure 4 - Mean value of % of MPS_{TFT} variation with gender

As shown in Figure 5, the work motivation of single IT Professionals was higher than that of the married category. According to Figure 6, the work motivation of IT professionals who belong to the category of less than 2 years of service in the current company was higher than that of the other two categories. MPS decreases when the number of years of service in the current company increases.

Figure 5 - Mean value of % of MPS_{TIT} variation with civil status

Figure 6 - Mean value of % of MPS_{TIT} variation with service in current

As shown in Figure 7, the work motivation of IT professionals who belong to the category of less than 4 years of service in the IT field was higher than that of the other two categories.

Figure 7 - Mean value of % of MPS_{TIT} variation with total service in IT field

Figure 8 - Mean value of % of MPS_{TIT} variation with no of employees

According to Figure 8, the work motivation of IT professionals who work in software companies with 50-200 employees was higher than that of the other three categories.

5. Conclusion

The findings of the study led to the implication that most of the hygiene factors, which were defined by Herzberg, moved towards the motivation direction, while most of the motivation factors, which were defined by Herzberg (1966), became less important motivation factors. This situation implied that the order of finding of this study was not in line with the order of the findings of Herzberg's study. Findings also implied that the software professionals are more satisfied with extrinsic motivators (Harry and Edward, 1998). As Salancik and Pfeffer's social information processing theory (1978) suggests, it is possible to argue that the entry of more extrinsically motivated individuals into the IT field in Sri Lanka might have made the IT field less attractive to those who are intrinsically motivated. Further, as suggested by Akuratiyagamage (2003) and Wickramasinghe (2006), development opportunities may play a prominent role. As suggested by Akuratiyagamage and Opatha (2003), IT professionals' grievances may provide clues to their dissatisfactions, such as workplace flexibility (Jayabandu and Wickramasinghe, 2006). Furthermore, results revealed that IT professionals' needs are more similar regardless of demographic groupings and the number of employees in the company in the Sri Lankan context. This implies that IT managers/employers need to pay special attention to factors that ranked higher and lower in designing IT-related jobs and in motivating IT professionals.

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